

Effect of Ultraviolet Light on Enzymatic Reactions. Part II. Pepsin.

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The influence of substances like urea, substituted ureas, organic and inorganic ammonium salts on the activity of proteoclastic enzymes, *e.g.*, pepsin, is the subject of investigation in the present paper. As the enzyme pepsin itself liberates amino-acids from protein matters by its action, the influence of the amino-acids like tyrosine, leucine, asparagine, glutamic acid, gelatine, egg-albumin, etc., could not be tried; their addition would be but to inhibit the direct action of pepsin on proteins. It has been found, as will be evident from the following table of results, that biuret, urea, substituted ureas and ammonium citrate produce a marked increase in the peptic activity of the enzyme. Organic ammonium salts, *viz.*, benzoate, oxalate, tartrate, etc., produce no increment in the activity of the enzyme. An exception, however, is to be found in the case of ammonium citrate which causes a distinct enhancement of the peptic activity. By comparing the results of diastase (*cf.* Banerjee and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 379) with those of pepsin, it is found that ammonium chloride, bromide, formate and benzoate produce no increment in the activities of either of the two enzymes, whereas ammonium citrate causes activation in both the cases. Biuret, urea, substituted ureas, while causing activation of pepsin, fail in the case of diastase. Diamines like *para* or *meta*-phenylenediamine, *m*-toluylenediamine had no effect in the activation of pepsin. It was seen that the diamines unlike the amines were also incapable of decomposing pyruvic acid even at the elevated temperature of 137° (*cf.* Banerjee and Sen, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1935, 1, 83). Attempts were also made to enhance the peptic activity further by treatment with ultraviolet light together with the so-called catalysts. Unlike diastase, (Banerjee and Sen, *loc. cit.*) the ultraviolet rays could not affect the activity of pepsin at the particular hydrogen-ion concentration of the substrate considered. The protein substrate itself might protect the enzyme from the destructive action of the ultraviolet rays, just as it will be remembered that the destruction of the diastatic activity by ultraviolet light (*cf.* Pincussen, *Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 134, 459;

1924, 144, 366; 1924, 152, 406) is considerably arrested by the addition of small quantities of protein matters, *e. g.*, albumin, gelatin, etc. (Banerjee and Sen, *loc. cit.*). The matter has been fully discussed previously. In the human system perhaps this protein matter protects the tissues from the injurious effect of the ultraviolet rays, for it is known that the rays cannot penetrate much below the epidermis of the human system.

As in the case of diastase, four sets of experiments were carried out in the case of pepsin also *viz.*, (i) without accelerator, (ii) with accelerator, (iii) with accelerator and ultraviolet light and (iv) without accelerator and with ultraviolet light.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Measurement of the peptic activity.—The measurement of the activity of the enzyme presented much technical difficulty at the outset. Sorensen's method of formol titration of the liberated amino-acids though conveniently applicable in the case of trypsin or Willstätter's method of thymolphthalein titration (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 2988; *cf.* also Harris, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923-24, B, 95, 500) was found not to be satisfactory in the present system of experiments. The measurements of the peptic activity were made by the comparative method of Gross (*Arch. Exp. Path. Pharmacol.*, 1906, 58, 157) who suggests a solution of very pure caseinogen as the protein substrate for the enzyme. The substrate is prepared by dissolving 1 g. of pure caseinogen in 16 c. c. of 25 % HCl (*d* 1.124) in a 1000 c.c. flask on a water-bath and diluting to 1000 c.c. The undigested caseinogen can be precipitated by a 20% solution of sodium acetate.

Preparation of pure caseinogen.—1000 C.c. of skimmed milk were diluted six times with water and the caseinogen precipitated by adding with constant stirring, about a litre of dilute acetic acid (10 to 15 c.c. of glacial acetic acid in 1000 c. c. of water), avoiding excess of the latter. The precipitate was allowed to settle and the solution decanted; the former was washed with large volume of distilled water, till free from acid. The precipitate was then dissolved in dilute ammonia to form a solution neutral to litmus. It was diluted with a large volume of water and the caseinogen reprecipitated with dilute acetic acid, avoiding excess of the latter. The precipitate was washed free from acid, redissolved in ammonia and reprecipitated with acid. The operation was repeated several times. The precipitate was finally filtered and

washed free from acid. It was then suspended in about 1000 c.c. of $N/10$ -HCl and churned for about 2 hours to remove the inorganic salts. The process was repeated. The precipitate was finally washed free from acid and treated several times with large volumes of alcohol and ether and dried at room temperature. It was finally ground and dried at $40-45^{\circ}$.

Procedure.—In each of a series of ten clean and numbered test tubes of approximately the same bore, are placed 10 c.c. of the acid caseinogen solution. The p_{H} of the caseinogen substrate was generally maintained at 1.8, the optimum for the pepsin reaction. The tubes with their contents were warmed to 40° in a constant temperature bath. To each of the tubes then a progressively increasing amount of the enzyme solution, *i.e.*, 0.1 c.c. in the first tube, 0.2 c.c. in the second, and so on, was added as quickly as possible. The series of test tubes was replaced in the bath and kept for half an hour. The tubes were then taken out and 1 c.c. of 20% sodium acetate solution was added very quickly to each tube; the undigested casein was precipitated. The smallest quantity of the enzyme required to digest the 10 c.c. of the caseinogen solution at the given time, is the value noted, *i.e.*, the first clear tube of the series is taken as the index. The turbidity and clarity of the contents of the tubes were finally checked by the nephelometer. If 1 c.c. of the pepsin solution be the basis of calculation and 0.025 c.c. was sufficient, then the pepsin solution corresponds to $1/0.025 = 40$ units. The enzyme solution used was generally a 2% solution of pepsin.

As in the experiments with diastase (Banerjee and Sen, *loc. cit.*), the p_{H} of the caseinogen substrate for pepsin was checked with and without the accelerators and always kept constant for the same set of experiments. This was necessary to show that the effect of the activators is not due to a more favourable hydrogen-ion concentration induced by their presence. That the action of the so-called activators is also not due to the deviation of the iso-electric point of precipitation of caseinogen induced by their presence, is evident from the fact that the p_{H} of the content of the tube taken as index, after the addition of the sodium acetate solution, was very near the iso-electric point of precipitation of caseinogen. Even the addition of very small amounts of $N/100$ -alkali to the 'index' tube did not make any precipitate appear, thus deviating the resulting p_{H} value more towards the iso-electric point of precipitation of caseinogen which is 4.7.

The experiments with ultraviolet light were carried out in quartz tubes and in an incubator adjusted at 40°. The exposure was generally for 15 minutes at a distance of two feet with a mercury-vapour lamp of 3000 C. P. and 12" arc. Further work with other proteoclastic enzymes, *e.g.*, papain, trypsin, etc., is in progress. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

1 C. c. of 0.1 % soln_s used. p_H of the substrate = 1.8.

Substance.	Control expt. Peptic value P ₁ .	With cata- lyst Peptic value P ₂ .	With cata- lyst and ultraviolet. Peptic value P ₃ .	Control expt. without catalyst with ultraviolet. Peptic value P ₄ .	pH of the 1st clear tube, after addition of Na-acetate soln.
Urea	2 units	2.5 units	2.5 units	2.0 units	4.4
Biuret	2.0	3.3	3.3	2.0	4.4
* Phenylurea	1.43	2.0	2.0	1.43	4.3
Thiourea	1.66	2.0	2.0	1.66	4.4
Phenylthiourea	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.0	4.4
Allylthiourea	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.0	4.4
Ammon. citrate	2.0	2.5	2.5	„	4.4
Ammon. oxalate	2.0	2.0	2.0	„	4.3
Ammon. benzoate	„	„	„	„	4.3
Ammon. tartrate	„	„	„	„	4.4
Ammon. bromide	„	„	„	„	4.3
Ammon. iocide	„	„	„	„	4.3
Ammon. chloride	„	„	„	„	4.4
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	„	„	„	„	4.4
<i>m</i> -Toluylenediamine	„	„	„	„	4.4

* p_H of the substrate in this case is 1.9.

DISCUSSION.

The idea that the enzyme is composed of a portion which is specifically catalytic and another portion which is essentially a colloidal substance, has been more or less established, from previous work. In

fact, the purification of an enzyme consists in eliminating unnecessary accompanying matters, leaving these two portions intact. The colloidal portion, however, may suffer greater and greater degree of dispersion (*cf.* Pincussen and co-workers, *Biochem. Z.*, 1924, **144**, 366; 1926, **171**, 1; 1928, **195**, 79; also Banerjee and Sen, *loc. cit.*) whilst the catalytic portion remains as before. This increased dispersion may no doubt be expected to increase the catalytic activity owing to the greater surface caused by dispersion, but at the same time it may also be conjectured that this increased dispersion produces susceptibility to easy de-activation. The influence of ions on the coagulation or "coarsening" of the colloid particles, has been held to be the reason for this de-activation. Pincussen and his school (*loc. cit.*) have laid special stress on this aspect. In their work on the influence of ultraviolet light on the activity of pepsin (*cf.* Pincussen and Kekusji Uehara, *Biochem. Z.*, 1928, **195**, 87) they have shown that the effect of a potassium ion is more de-activating than that of calcium ion. This characteristic, however, is not throughout maintained. In another series of experiments, they have shown that the action of ultraviolet light on the hydrolysis of fibrin by pepsin is negligible if the p_H value lies between 1.93 and 2.28. Between the p_H values 1.15 and 1.42, the de-activation of the enzyme appears to be distinct and prominent. In other words, with stronger acidity, the difference between the hydrolytic capacities in ultraviolet and in the absence of ultraviolet, is very much noticeable. Specially, working at p_H 1.15—1.19 according to the present method, however, no such action of ultraviolet light as reported by Pincussen was noticed by us.

It is a question that should be asked here, what is the optimum p_H value for the hydrolysis of fibrin on one hand, and other types of proteins on the other by pepsin. Thus for caseinogen the optimal p_H value for the hydrolytic action of pepsin, has been laid down to be 1.8 (Northrop, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1919, **1**, 607; 1920, **3**, 211; 1922, **5**, 263), whereas from Pincussen's experiments with ox-fibrin or sheep-fibrin, 1.15-1.17 appears to be the optimum; in the experiments of the present paper (where the method of determining the hydrolytic activity of pepsin is different) at the optimum p_H of 1.8, there does not appear to be any difference in the hydrolysis of caseinogen whether under the influence of ultraviolet or without it. It is in this region of p_H value that Pincussen and his collaborators also find no influence of ultraviolet light on the activity of pepsin on fibrin.

One must notice here that the values of the hydrolytic decomposition of the proteid matter by pepsin may be different according to the method of determination of the peptic value.

In Sorensen's work (*Biochem. Z.*, 1909, 21, 131), it has been shown that the optimal action of pepsin, measured in the digestion of egg-albumin, corresponds to a strongly acid reaction, the optimal p_H being about 1.5, if the duration of the experiment is short; upon more prolonged or extensive transformation, however, there is noticed a considerable expansion in the region of optimal activity in the direction of lower acidity. The cause of this change has not yet been recognised. According to Northrop (*loc. cit.*) the dependence of the action of pepsin is influenced, like that of other proteolytic enzymes, by the ionisation state of the substrates used. According to this view, the action of pepsin is to be attributed to its reaction with protein cations. Its p_H optimum is then displaced at the same time as the i o-electric point of the substrate. The optimum p_H for the hydrolysis of caseinogen by pepsin has been found to be 1.8 and that for hæmoglobin and gelatine 2.2. The results obtained in the present investigations for the optimum p_H dependence of pepsin for the hydrolysis of casein, are given in Table II. The nature of the reactions is such that if activity— p_H , curve is drawn it will be found that with the increase of p_H , peptic value rises till it reaches a maximum and then it tends to decrease.

TABLE II.

p_H values	...	1.4	1.6	1.8	2.0	2.2
Peptic values	...	1.66	1.818	2.00	1.75	1.43

One notices the fundamental difference that whilst Pincussen and others had fibrin in an undissolved state for the pepsin to act upon, in the present case caseinogen was obtained in an optically clear solution for the enzyme to work upon. This no doubt would ensure a greater homogeneity in the hydrolytic decomposition of the protein, and in fact, place the analytical data on a better foundation. The uncertainties of the soluble amino-acid adsorption on the undissolved fibrin to which Pincussen refers in his work, have thus no influence in the method of determination followed in the present case. To explain the so-called de-activating influence of ultraviolet light at lower p_H concentrations (*cf.* Pincussen and Uehara, *loc. cit.*), one must look for an explanation which is dependent on the ionic activity

under the influence of ultraviolet light (*vide supra*). At higher hydrogen-ion concentration, probably the colloidal particles of the enzyme-complex which are already sensitive to the action of ultraviolet light are transformed into bigger particles, thus rendering the enzyme-complex less active. That at a slightly higher p_H value (1.8) there is no de-activation, may be due to the dimension of the colloidal particles themselves. In other words between p_H 1.15 and 1.42, the degree of dispersion of the colloid particles is probably such that they are in that state most affected by light percussions. Whether one could not correlate the dimensions of the particles of the enzyme-complex at this stage of dispersion and the wave-lengths of the lights, is a matter for consideration. An alternative idea to explain the non-de-activation at p_H 1.8 may be found in the assumption, that at that hydrogen-ion concentration, the enzyme-complex forms a further complex with the acid or its ions, which is not sensitive to the action of ultraviolet light. The exploration of the catalytic activities of the enzyme both below and above the optimal p_H regions under the influence of ultraviolet light would be of great importance in understanding the nature of the enzyme-complex itself. It seems clear, however, from the present work that the general characteristic of proteins to act as a protector against the ultraviolet rays in the case of diastase (*loc. cit.*) is maintained here also.

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